

Demographic Profile, Etiology and Disease Severity of Patients of Liver Cirrhosis in a Tertiary Care Hospital of Punjab (North-West India)**Amolpreet Kaur^{1*}, Manish Chandey², Gurinder Mohan³, Parminder Singh⁴, Amandeep Kaur⁵**¹Senior Resident, Department of Medicine, Sri Guru Ram Das Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Sri Amritsar, Punjab, India, 143001.²Professor, Department of Medicine, Sri Guru Ram Das Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Sri Amritsar, Punjab, India, 143001.³Professor and Head, Department of Medicine, Sri Guru Ram Das Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Sri Amritsar, Punjab, India, 143001.⁴Senior Medical Officer, Department of Medicine, ESIC Hospital, Ludhiana, Punjab, India, 141001.⁵Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Sri Guru Ram Das Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Sri Amritsar, Punjab, India, 143001.

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Abstract:**Introduction:** Cirrhosis of liver is one of the leading causes of hospitalization and mortality worldwide. It is defined by fibrosis of liver parenchyma and formation of regenerative nodules. The rate at which chronic liver disease progresses into cirrhosis is variable and depends upon the underlying etiology and patient characteristics.**Aim:** This study was conducted in a tertiary care hospital of Punjab (North- West India) on patients of liver cirrhosis. The aim of the study is to highlight the demographic profile, etiology, clinical presentation and disease severity of liver cirrhosis.**Objectives:**

1. To study the demographic profile of patients of liver cirrhosis.
2. To study the etiology of liver disease in the patient population.
3. To estimate the severity of liver disease using Child Pugh Score and MELD-Na score.

Materials and Methods: This cross-sectional study was conducted from May, 2021 to July, 2022 at a tertiary care hospital on 150 patients of liver cirrhosis. The demographic profile and clinical history were obtained. Ultrasonographic findings were noted. Serum biochemical parameters were sent and Child Pugh and MELD- Na score was calculated for each study participant. The cumulative data was analysed during the study period.**Result:**

1. Highest incidence of cirrhosis of liver was found in the age group 51-60years.
2. Males were affected more commonly than females with a Male: Female ratio of 5.8: 1.
3. Most common etiology of cirrhosis was Alcoholic liver disease. Hepatitis C was the second most common cause, followed by Nonalcoholic Steatohepatitis and Hepatitis B.
4. Hepatic encephalopathy and ascites were the most common complications, followed by splenomegaly, variceal bleed and spontaneous bacterial peritonitis.
5. The mean serum albumin, bilirubin, prothrombin time and platelets were 2.42± 0.67 g/dl, 4.88± 3.15 mg/dl, 20.94± 8.34 sec and 1.64± 0.98lac/ml respectively.
6. Out of total 150 patients, 10.67% were in Child Class A (n=16), 38% were in Child Class B(n=57) and 51.33 % patients(n=77) were in Child class C(n=77).
7. 52% patients (n=79) were in MELD-Na category 10-19 (n=79), 32% patients(n=48) were in MELD-Na category 20-29 (n=48), 8.67% were in MELD-Na category <9 (n=13) and 6.67% patients were in MELD-Na category 30-39 (n=10) and no patient was found in MELD-Na category >40.

Conclusion: The study indicates that Alcoholic Liver Disease is the most common etiology of liver cirrhosis in Punjab (North- West India). Males are affected more than females. Highest prevalence is found in the age group of 51-60years. Hepatic encephalopathy and ascites are the most common complications of liver cirrhosis. Maximum number of patients present to hospital in Child Class C and MELD-Na score category 10-19.**Keywords:** Liver cirrhosis, Child Pugh score, MELD- Na score, Ascites, Hepatic encephalopathy, Etiology, Alcoholic Liver Disease.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access

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Introduction

Cirrhosis of liver is one of the top 10 leading causes of death. Globally, mortality of cirrhosis has increased by 47.15% from 1990 to 2017. India had observed the maximum number of deaths in 2017 from cirrhosis across the globe. The age standardized rate of mortality caused by chronic hepatitis C (HCV), alcohol consumption and non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH) has increased with an estimated annual percentage change of 0.17, 0.20, 1.00 respectively. [1] A prospective study was conducted over 20 million patients from various parts of India which showed prevalence of chronic liver disease to be 1.28% among the population. Alcohol was the most common etiology for cirrhosis (33.3%). Hepatitis C was estimated to be the commonest cause for chronic liver disease in North-India, Alcohol in the North-East India, Hepatitis B in the Eastern and the Southern parts, while Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) was most common etiology in the West. [2]

Portal hypertension is the earliest manifestation of liver cirrhosis and is responsible for majority of the complications. A combination of clinical suspicion, laboratory diagnosis and imaging can help confirm the diagnosis of liver cirrhosis. The triad of portal hypertension comprises of ascites, splenomegaly and varices. Clinical features suggestive of

cirrhosis occur due to alterations in the estrogen metabolism by the cirrhotic liver. Palmar erythema, terry's nails, finger clubbing, gynecomastia, parotid enlargement, spider telangiectasias and caput medusae are clinical signs of suggestive of intrahepatic portal hypertension. [3]

Elevation of serum bilirubin is seen late in the disease; however cholestatic etiology may show elevation of serum bilirubin before cirrhosis. Liver is the site for albumin synthesis and it falls with deterioration in hepatic function. Hepatic coagulopathy includes deranged Prothrombin time (PTI-INR) which rises when hepatic ability to generate clotting factors deteriorates. Hyponatremia is seen due to inability to excrete free water is in the presence of cirrhosis with ascites. Indirect markers of cirrhosis include, The AST: ALT ratio. The normal ratio of Aspartate aminotransferase (SGOT) to alanine aminotransferase (SGPT) is 0.8. When the ratio exceeds 1.0, it provides some evidence of cirrhosis. Another index is the AST: Platelet ratio (APRI), which calculated as: $AST / \text{Upper limit of normal for AST} \times 100 / \text{Platelet count} (\times 10^9/L)$. Depending upon the cut-off, it is highly specific for diagnosing cirrhosis. [4]

Table 1: Calculation of the Child–Pugh Score -The Severity of Cirrhosis Is Graded As: Child-Pugh A: (5 To 6 Points), Child-Pugh B: (7 To 9 Points) and Child-Pugh C: (10 To 15 Points) [4]

Parameters	1	2	3
Bilirubin (mg/mL)	<2	2-3	>3
Albumin(mg/mL)	>3.5	2.8-3.5	<2.8
INR	<1.7	1.7-2.2	>2.2
Ascites	None	Slight	Moderate
Encephalopathy	None	Grade 1 and 2	Grade 3 and 4

Table 2: Child Pugh Turcot Score as a Marker of Prognosis in Patients of Cirrhosis of Liver [5]

Class	Points	Survival At 1 Year (%)	Survival At 2 Years (%)
Child Class A	5-6	100	85
Child Class B	7-9	80	60
Child Class C	10-15	45	35

The formula for MELD score calculation is as followed: $9.6 \log_e (\text{creatinine mg/dl}) + 3.8 \log_e (\text{bilirubin mg/dl}) + 11.2 \log_e (\text{INR}) + 6.4$. Serum sodium was incorporated in the prognostic model, by calculation of the MELD-Na score according to the formula given by Biggins: $MELD + 1.59 (135 - \text{serum sodium})$

Table 3: Interpretation of Meld-Na Score [6]

MELD/Na score	Mortality (%)
>40	71.3
30-39	52.6
20-29	19.6
10-19	6.0
<9	1.9

Materials and Methods:

Study Design: Cross-sectional study.

Participants: The study was conducted from 1st April, 2021 to 31st July, 2022 in a tertiary care hospital of Punjab (North-West India) on the patients of cirrhosis of liver of any etiology, with or without its complications.

Method of Data Collection: A complete history was obtained and thorough clinical examination was done and complications of cirrhosis and portal hypertension were identified in the patients.

Patients were subjected to laboratory work up for chronic liver disease.

Laboratory Investigations: 10ml of venous blood sample was withdrawn from each individual under aseptic conditions and divided into three aliquots. 1.8ml of whole blood was collected in Sodium Citrate 3.2% (1:9) vial and centrifuged for 4mins at 1500rpm for the estimation of Prothrombin time. 2ml blood was collected in EDTA BD vacutainer for estimation of Complete blood count.

Rest of the blood was allowed to clot and serum was separated after 20 min by remicentrifuge machine at 3000 rpm for the estimation of the all the other biochemical parameters on VITROS 5600 system Integrated Method.

Details of the methods used for the quantification of all the biochemical parameters are given below-

- SGOT (AST), SGPT (ALT) measurement via Reagent UV with PSP method.
- Alkaline Phosphatase measurement via PMPP, AMP buffer technique.
- Serum Bilirubin measurement (total) by Reagent Jendrassik Grof method and Bilirubin

(Direct/Indirect) via Dedicated reagent diazotization.

- Total Protein estimation via Biuret, Reagent blank endpoint method and serum albumin was measured using Bromocresol purple.
- BUN estimation via Urease Calorimetric Method and serum creatinine estimation via alkaline pikrate kinetic method.
- Serum Sodium and Potassium was measured using Ion Selective Electrode Indirect method.
- Serum Prolactin levels via dedicated reagent enhanced chemiluminescence assay.
- Prothrombin time estimation was done via TCOAG: Destiny Plus setup.
- Complete blood counts estimated by Beckman Counter Coulter LH 780 Analyzer.
- Hepatitis B Antigen (HBsAg) and anti-Hepatitis C Virus (HCV) antibodies via ELISA.

Ultrasonography was performed for evaluation of liver status, portal vein diameter, ascites and splenomegaly. Diagnostic paracentesis of ascitic fluid was done under all aseptic precautions during which 10ml of ascitic fluid was collected and sent for the analysis for biochemistry Serum ascitic albumin gradient was calculated to determine the cause of ascites. Ascitic fluid cytology was sent to rule out Spontaneous Bacterial Peritonitis. The patients who presented with history suggestive of GI bleed, were subjected to upper gastrointestinal endoscopy for diagnostic and therapeutic purpose.

The modified Child Pugh Score was calculated for each study participant. The patients were classified into Class A, B and C according to the score obtained.

Hepatic encephalopathy was diagnosed and graded as per West Haven Classification system.

Table 4: Diagnosis and Grading of Hepatic Encephalopathy as Per West Haven Criteria⁷

Stage	Consciousness	Intellect And Behaviour	Neurological Findings
0	Normal.	Normal.	Normal examination; if psychomotor testing is impaired, then minimal HE.
Grade I	Mild lack of awareness.	Shortened attention span; impaired addition or subtraction.	Mild asterixis or tremor.
Grade II	Lethargic.	Disoriented; inappropriate behavior.	Obvious asterixis; slurred speech.
Grade III	Somnolent but arousable.	Gross disorientation; bizarre behavior.	Muscular rigidity and clonus; Hyperreflexia.
Grade IV	Coma	Coma	Decerebrate posturing

Statistical Analysis: All the data was stored into Microsoft Office 2007. For analysis of continuous variables, Student's - t test and One-Way ANOVA test were used.

Observations: Demographic Profile: Age: The highest incidence was found in the age group (51-60 years) in 27.33 % patients (n=41).

Figure 1: Showing age distribution of the study population

Sex: In our study population, 85.3% (n= 128) were males and 14.67% (n= 22) were females, with a ratio of 5.8:1.

Figure 2: This shows the sex distribution of study population

Clinical Presentation: Figure 3 shows that in our study participants, 46.66% patients (n=70) had a chief complaint of abdominal distension, 43.33% patients (n=65) had pedal edema, 26.66% patients (n=40) had history of altered talks, 36% patients (n=54) had complaint of yellowish discoloration of eyes, 9.33%patients (n=14) had of hematemesis, and 4.66% patients(n=7) had melena on presentation.

Figure 3: Clinical Presentation of the study population

Table 5: Etiology of Cirrhosis:

Etiology	No. of Cases	%Age
Alcoholic	90	60.00
NASH	21	14.00

HBV	5	3.33
HBV+Alcoholic	4	2.67
HCV	16	10.67
HCV+Alcoholic	8	5.33
Others	6	4.00
Total	150	100.00

Table 5 and Figure 4, shows the etiological distribution of cirrhosis in the 150 patients who presented to us, out of which 60% (n=90) were alcoholic, 14% (n=2) were Nonalcoholic Steatohepatitis, 10.67% patients (n=16) were Hepatitis C positive, 5.3% (n=8) were Hepatitis C positive who were also alcoholic, 3.3% patients (n=5) were Hepatitis B positive, 2.67% (n=4) were Hepatitis B and alcoholic.

Figure 4: Distribution of the study population according to etiology of cirrhosis

Table 6: Distribution of the study population as per level of hepatic encephalopathy (West Haven Criteria)

Grade of Hepatic Encephalopathy	No. Of Cases	Percentage(%)
None	55	36.66
Grade I	25	16.66
Grade II	31	20.66
Grade III	37	24.66
Grade IV	2	1.33

Table 6 and Figure 5 shows the distribution of patients according to West Haven Criteria of hepatic encephalopathy. 36.66 % patients(n=55) were having no evidence of encephalopathy, 16.66%(n=25) were having Grade I encephalopathy ,20.66% (n=31) had Grade II encephalopathy, 24.66%(n=33) had grade III encephalopathy and 1.33%(n=2) had Grade IV encephalopathy.

Figure 5: Distribution of the study population according to Hepatic Encephalopathy (West Haven Criteria)

Table 7: Distribution of Study Population as Per Child PUGH Score

CPS Class	No. of cases	% Age
A	16	10.67
B	57	38.00
C	77	51.33
Total	150	100.00

Table 7 and Figure 6 shows the distribution of patients according to Child Pugh Score. 10.67% were in Child Class A (n=16), 38% were in Child Class B (n=57) and 51.33 % patients (n=77) were in Child class C(n=77).

Figure 6: Distribution of study population according to Child Pugh Score

Table 8: Distribution of Study Population According to Meld-Na Score

MELD-Na	No. of cases	% Age
<9	13	8.67
10-19	79	52.67
20-29	48	32.00
30-39	10	6.67
>40	0	0.00
Total	150	100.00

Table 8 and Figure 7 shows that out of total 150 patients who presented to us, 79% patients(n=79) were in MELD-Na category 10-19 (n=79), 32% patients(n=48) were in MELD-Na category 20-29 (n=48), 8.67% were in MELD-Na category <9 (n=13) and 6.67% patients were in MELD-Na category 30-39(n=10) and no patient was found in MELD-Na category >40.

Figure 7: Distribution of patients according to MELD-Na Score

Table 9: Ultrasonographic Findings in the Study Population

Usg Findings	Number of Cases	Percentage (%)
Cirrhosis	150	100
Ascites	92	61.33%
Splenomegaly	62	41.33
Portal Vein Thrombus	4	2.66
Hepatic Vein Thrombus	1	0.06

Table 9 and Figure 8 shows the distribution of ultrasonographic findings in our study population. Out of 150 patients, 100% patients (n=150) had cirrhosis of liver, 61.33% patients(n=92) had ascites, 41.33% patients(n=62) had splenomegaly, 2.66%(n=4) had portal vein thrombus and 0.06% (n=1) patient had thrombus in the hepatic vein.

Figure 8: Distribution of ultrasonographic findings in the study population

Table 10: Distribution of Complications of Cirrhosis in the Study Population

Complications Of Cirrhosis	No. Of Cases	Percentage(%)
Ascites	92	61.33
Splenomegaly	62	41.33
Variceal Bleed	18	12.00
Sontaneous Bacterial Peritonitis	11	7.33
Encephalopathy	95	63.33

Table 10 and Figure 9 depicts the distribution of complications of cirrhosis in our study population. Among 150 patients, 63.33% patients (n=25) had evidence of encephalopathy in them, 61.3%patients (n=92) had ascites, 41.3% (n=62) had splenomegaly, 12% (n=18) had variceal bleed,7.33% (n=11) were having SBP.

Figure 9: Distribution of complications of cirrhosis in the study population

Table 11: Mean Distribution of Lab Parameters According To the Child Pugh Score

Lab Parameters	CPS A	CPS B	CPS C
Hemoglobin	10.83	9.50	9.27
Total Leucocyte Count	6994	7378	9426

Platelets	2.08	1.69	1.51
Total Bilirubin	1.04	2.41	7.50
Ast	82.09	99.85	136.82
Alt	70.18	57.47	76.99
Alkaline Phosphatase	180.90	176.27	164.27
Creatinine	1.37	1.02	1.00
Bun	11.10	12.07	16.44
Sodium	136.25	136.35	134.48
Potassium	4.25	4.23	4.15

Table 11 shows the distribution of various lab parameters in our study population.

Discussion:

Demographic Profile: In the present study, it was observed that the highest incidence of cirrhosis was found in the age group 51-60 years with 27.33 % patients (n=41). Similarly, the mean age was 56 years in the study conducted by Ressa C et al [7], 51.94±5.99 years by Khaleel FM et al [8], 44±12.8 years by Puneekar P et al [9], 47 years by Ramini MS et al [10], 52.94 ± 6.99 years by Patel et al [11], 47 years by Animesh et al [12] and 56 years by Sumit et al [13]. In the present study, the males were affected more than females with a ratio of 5.8:1. This was similar to that seen in the past, with the male: female ratio of 2:1 in the study by Ressa C et al [7], 1.4:1 by Patel et al [11], 4:1 by Animesh et al [12], 2:1 by Sumit et al [13], 1.6:1 by Ramy et al [14], 3.5:1 by Vikash et al [15] and 4.8:1 by Rajasekarapandian et al [16].

Etiology: In the present study, alcohol was the most common etiology seen in 60% patients (n=90), followed by NASH in 14% (n=21), HCV in 10.67% patients (n=16), HCV and alcohol together in 5.3% (n=8), HBV in 3.3% patients (n=5) and HBV and alcohol in 2.67% (n=4) patients.

This was similar to other studies conducted by Puneekar et al [9], where alcohol was the most common etiological cause in 55% patients, followed by HBV in 18.3% and other causes in 7.8% of the patients. Also, in the study by Ramini et al [10], alcohol was the most common etiology in 68% patients, followed by HBV in 12%. Vikash et al [15] also had alcohol as the most common etiology in 74% patients, which was followed by HCV in 12% and HBV in 4%. Similarly in the study by Balakrishna CH et al [17], alcohol was found to be the most common etiology (73%). Also, in the study by, Paternostro et al [18] alcoholic liver disease was the most common in (53.5%) patients, followed by viral in (26.3%) patients, and others causes in (20.2%). Sakhnani et al [19] also had alcoholic cirrhosis found in 56% of the study population, as the most common etiology. Giri et al [20] also had alcoholic liver disease (45.71%) as the most common cause for cirrhosis and viral hepatitis, both HBV (22.85 %) and HCV (14.29%) are the next common causes of cirrhosis.

On the contrary, Zacharias et al [21] had 10 patients (33.33%) of HCV, 8(26.67%) of alcohol abuse, 3(10% of NASH) and 2 (6.67%) of HBV. Overall, we found alcohol as the most common etiology for cirrhosis of liver.

Complications of Cirrhosis: Among the distribution of complications of cirrhosis in our study population, in a total of 150 patients, 63.33% patients (n=25) had hepatic encephalopathy, 61.3%patients (n=92) had ascites, 41.3% (n=62) had splenomegaly, 12% (n=18) had variceal bleed and 7.33% (n=11) had SBP. Similarly, in the study conducted by Animesh et al [12], ascites was seen in 98.5% patients, and hepatic encephalopathy 71.42%, esophageal varices in 62.85% and hematemesis 44.3% patients.

Balakrishna CH et al [17] found the most common complications as portal hypertension in 83.3%, esophageal varices in 65%, and hematemesis in 36.7% and hepatic encephalopathy in 25% patients. Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis in 8.33% (n=5) and hepatorenal syndrome in 5% (n=3) patients. So, ascites and hepatic encephalopathy were the most common complications which were followed by variceal bleed, SBP and HRS.

Conclusions

The following are the key observations of our study:

1. Highest incidence of cirrhosis of liver is found in the age group 51-60years.
2. Males are affected more commonly than females with a Male: Female ratio of 5.8:1.
3. Most common etiology of cirrhosis is Alcoholic liver disease, followed by Hepatitis C, NASH and Hepatitis B.
4. The most common complications of cirrhosis in our study population include hepatic encephalopathy and ascites, which is followed by splenomegaly, variceal bleed and SBP.
5. The maximum patients 51.33% are seen in Child Class C (n=77), followed by 38% in Child Class B(n=57) and 10.67% were in Child Class A (n=16).
6. The maximum number of patients i.e. 51.33% were in MELD-Na category 10-19, followed

by 32% in category 20-29, 8.67% in category <9 and 6.67% in category 30-39.

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